

UNDERSTANDING VOCABULARY KNOWLEDGE OF SECONDARY STUDENTS: A CONVERGENT STUDY

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Understanding Vocabulary Knowledge of Secondary Students: A Convergent Study

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Abstract

The study "Understanding Vocabulary Knowledge of Secondary Students: A Convergent Study" explores the vocabulary proficiency of Grade 10 students at Saint Jude Academy in Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Utilizing a convergent parallel mixed-method approach, the research integrates quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to gauge the students' vocabulary knowledge across three key indicators: vocabulary form, vocabulary meaning, and vocabulary use. Findings reveal that students generally demonstrate a low level of vocabulary knowledge, with struggles in comprehension, pronunciation, and contextual application. Key psychological and motivational factors impacting vocabulary acquisition emerged, such as emotional satisfaction when learning new words and barriers like disinterest in English. Challenges in vocabulary comprehension and formation—like difficulties with word recall, understanding synonyms and antonyms, and grammatical usage—were significant. The study highlights the need for more engaging, student-centered vocabulary instruction to boost students' vocabulary knowledge and language skills. These insights aim to support educators in refining vocabulary teaching strategies, thereby enhancing students' language competence and readiness for academic success.

Keywords: *vocabulary, knowledge, students, convergent*

Introduction

Vocabulary knowledge is regarded as an essential tool for mastering any language skills that contributes to the understanding of written and spoken texts. It serves as a critical tool for second language learners (Bhakti & Marwanto, 2018). However, mastering vocabulary can pose significant challenges, especially for individuals who lack the essential skills of defining words, discovering synonyms and antonyms, and applying these terms in various contexts. Additionally, Rohimajaya (2021) asserts that without learning vocabulary, attaining language proficiency and effective communication in the second language become harder.

Consequently, a study at Prince Stattam bin Abdulaziz University (PSAU) in Saudi Arabia revealed that Arab students, particularly non-native English speakers, found learning vocabulary to be challenging. Their difficulties included understanding new word meanings, spelling, pronunciation, proper word usage, and inferring meanings from context. As such, Arab students encountered hurdles in communicating effectively in English due to limited vocabulary knowledge, which impedes the learners' language comprehension and language use. The study also highlighted the impact of teachers' ineffective practices in teaching English in Saudi Arabia, where traditional methods and heavy reliance on the students' native language hindered their vocabulary development. The study, therefore, revealed that vocabulary plays a vital role in teaching and learning the second language as lexical knowledge is fundamental to communicate effectively. Thus, without vocabulary, the learners will be de-motivated to use the language (Richards & Renandya, 2018).

Similarly, in the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) presented data indicating a decrease in the performance of the country's public high school students compared to public elementary students in the National Achievement Test (NAT). According to DepEd's information, the average NAT score for public high school students from 2011 to 2012 was notably lower at 48.9% compared to the elementary students' 66.79%. This trend has persisted for the past five years. To investigate further, researchers focused on Manuel A. Roxas Elementary School in Davao City, known for its poor NAT performance. Recent data from the 2015 NAT results revealed that no student had achieved mastery level (96-100%), few were close to mastery (86-95%), and the majority were at levels below mastery, with all students falling within the average level of 35-65%. This data suggests that students did not meet the achievement standards set by the Department of Education. Consequently, the researchers concluded that the declining NAT performance might be attributed to a lack of vocabulary knowledge, hindering students' comprehension of what they read (Orbeta, 2020).

Recent advancements in acquiring second and foreign languages emphasize that, beyond grammar and pronunciation, non-native speakers must possess a strong vocabulary foundation to effectively use English in academic settings. Irrespective of learners' proficiency in grammar and pronunciation, inadequate vocabulary impedes their ability to communicate effectively as they struggle to comprehend contextual meanings within conversations (Viera, 2018). In line with this, the researcher was driven to conduct this study because secondary students began dealing with complex subjects that demand a sophisticated understanding of language. Therefore, conducting this study is imperative for secondary students to provide an understanding to building a strong vocabulary that would enable them to succeed academically and foster self-preparedness for future academic endeavors.

The exploration of vocabulary knowledge has been the subject of various studies. Such as the study conducted by Karuppiah (2022), "An investigation of vocabulary knowledge on students' writing performance," the study of Kilic (2019), "Vocabulary Knowledge as a Predictor of Performance in Writing and Speaking: A Case of Turkish EFL Learners," and the study entitled "Vocabulary Knowledge

in Relation to Students' Reading Comprehension: A Review" by Susanto (2018), however, these studies mainly focused on how vocabulary knowledge is associated with the writing performance and reading comprehension of international college students. Hence, none of these studies dealt with the understanding of vocabulary knowledge of secondary students, particularly using a mixed-methods approach, making their studies distinct from the study I have undertaken. Moreover, this study anticipates to offer an understanding of the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in a local private school in Maniki, Kapalong Davao del Norte.

Research Questions

This study aims to understand the vocabulary knowledge among secondary students, using a mixed methods research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to address the research problem at hand. This research design allowed for the strengths of each data collection method to offset the limitations of the other, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem through the combined analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data. This seeks to answer the following research questions.

1. What is the level of vocabulary knowledge among secondary students?
2. What is the perception of secondary students with regards to their vocabulary knowledge?
3. What are the insights of secondary students with regards to vocabulary knowledge?
4. To what degree do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods design, which involves the interlinking of qualitative and quantitative components to provide a more comprehensive account of the research problem. According to Halcomb and Hickman (2015), this integration is crucial for the rigor of the mixed methods research, and it can occur at any stage(s) of the research process. The term "mixing" refers to the process of linking the qualitative and quantitative elements to produce a fuller account of the research problem.

According to Bryman (2007), mixed methods research plays a vital role in research beyond mere validation. It enables the integration of multiple research methods, leading to a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the subject of study. This approach not only validates the research but also allows for a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By combining the results obtained from different methods, researchers can potentially reveal new insights that might have been overlooked using a single-method approach.

The research design selected for this study was a convergent parallel mixed method. In this design, both types of data are collected concurrently and given equal priority. The survey was collected first, followed by focus group or one-on-one interviews. The two sets of data are analyzed separately, and the results are then merged, with the combined results being interpreted. This design is appropriate for the study as it aims to explore the convergence, divergence, contradictions, or relationships between the two sources of data (Hanson et al., 2005).

The convergent parallel design, also known as the convergent/triangulation design, involves the simultaneous implementation of both quantitative and qualitative studies during the same phase of the research process. In this design, both methods have equal priority, enabling them to play an equally important role in addressing the research problem. This design maintains the independence of the studies during data collection and analysis and then merges or combines the results during the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

This study used a mixed-method approach called the convergent parallel design to obtain a thorough grasp of the subject. The two parts of the research process are the qualitative and the quantitative (Morse, 1991). When using a convergent parallel design, the researcher conducts both the quantitative and qualitative components of the study simultaneously at the same phase of the process, giving equal weight to each approach, assessing each component separately, and interpreting the findings jointly. By directly contrasting the quantitative statistical data with qualitative discoveries, the researcher hopes to triangulate the methodologies for validation and corroboration. Two datasets were acquired, examined independently, and then compared as part of the research process (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

Under a convergent parallel design, data from qualitative sources such as face-to-face interviews, audio recordings, and transcriptions, were collected alongside quantitative data obtained from a test questionnaire. These data were analyzed simultaneously to uncover patterns and insights. For the qualitative phase, a discourse and thematic analysis were used in order to analyze the understanding of secondary students with regard to vocabulary knowledge. For the quantitative data, statistical analysis was employed to get the results on the profiling, experiences of secondary students, significant difference in the status and extent on how quantitative data corroborate qualitative data.

Consequently, this research employed a descriptive-comparative approach, which involved comparing and contrasting the collected results to draw meaningful conclusions. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to provide an understanding of vocabulary knowledge necessary for building a strong vocabulary skill in comprehending complex texts, engage in higher-level discussions, and succeed in attaining language proficiency. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative

research methods (Richardson, 2018).

In addition, phenomenological inquiry was utilized in this study to further develop the qualitative frame. This methodology assisted the discovery and understanding within the rich environment evolving within the experiences of the participants. A phenomenology focuses on the commonality of experience within a particular group. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data such as documents and observations were also used (Creswell, 2013).

On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study utilized phenomenological approach, which reflects an epistemological perspective that acknowledges the validity of multiple subjective truths. Qualitative data collection methods such as focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews were also employed effectively to glean insights into the social norms of the community, saturate the data obtained from in-depth interviews, and establish themes based on the researcher's collected data (Groenewald, 2004).

Participants

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study are Grade 10 students enrolled in Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao at Maniki, Kapalong Davao del Norte. They were chosen as the respondents because the study mainly focused on the target participants. Since the study purports on understanding the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students, it would be fitting and valid to include grade 10 students at a local private secondary schools.

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or "strata," and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples are then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020). This sampling method is particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, which are Grade 10 students were randomly selected based on strata which in this case are all the grade 10 students in Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Participants*

<i>Section</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Saint Ann	41	34	42.49%
Saint Monica	41	34	42.49%
Total	82	68	84.98%

This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population have equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the school and gained access to the population of all grade 10 students. The researcher then gathered the data from the population of secondary students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for computation of the study sample. The study was conducted among grade 10 students enrolled in Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao. The institution has a total of 82 grade 10 students, consisting of two sections, Saint Ann and Saint Monica. Saint Ann has a population of 41, as does Saint Monica. However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which included 34 out of 41 students in section Saint Ann, while in section Saint Monica, 34 out of 41 students were included as well. In total, 68 students were sampled out of the 82 grade 10 students.

Qualitative Phase

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	Grade-10
IDI-02	Female	Grade-10
IDI-03	Female	Grade-10
IDI-04	Female	Grade-10
IDI-05	Female	Grade-10
IDI-06	Female	Grade-10
IDI-07	Male	Grade-10
FGD-01	Female	Grade-10
FGD-02	Male	Grade-10
FGD-03	Male	Grade-10
FGD-04	Female	Grade-10
FGD-05	Female	Grade-10
FGD-06	Female	Grade-10
FGD-07	Female	Grade-10

In contrast, subject selection in qualitative research was purposeful. In this phase, non-probability sampling specifically purposive sampling technique was utilized. Participants were selected who can best inform the research questions and enhance understanding of

the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). Only 14 participants of secondary students will be enjoined in the qualitative phase: seven (7) for in-depth interview and another seven (7) for focus group discussion. All of them should be a grade 10 students enrolled in private school of Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao. It should be noted that participants in qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of quantitative phases.

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher used the researcher-made test questionnaires that suited the content of the study. The test questionnaires had the following indicators: vocabulary form, vocabulary meaning, and vocabulary use.

Notably, the test is exclusively composed of multiple-choice questions, where participants choose only one answer out of the list of available options, and is the format most commonly associated with multiple-choice questions, emphasizing a structured and systematic approach to evaluating the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students. The vocabulary knowledge has three indicators: vocabulary form, vocabulary meaning, and vocabulary use. Each indicator is composed of ten (10) items. The researcher-made test questionnaire was subjected to expert validation to ensure its content validity. To interpret the perception of organizational commitment, the range of means, description, and interpretation were presented below.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, seven were purposively selected to undergo the IDI and another seven for the FGD. Interviews were suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

There were several steps in the data collection process. The following procedures were followed during the conduct of the study:

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, a researcher-made test questionnaire was used for understanding vocabulary knowledge of secondary students. In addition, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the school administrator, asking an approval to conduct the study to their respective school and students. The results were tallied, computed and analyzed to corroborate with the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were done simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview was conducted to the identified participants in order to gather the perspectives of these secondary students with regard to their vocabulary knowledge. An Interview guide was used both for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Hence, to ensure authenticity of selection, the researcher invited through personal contact the informants and they were informed of the tasks to be and that includes the time set for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013).

The focus group discussion centered on the exploration of individuals' opinions, experiences, concerns, and desires regarding the specific issues at hand. According to Traynor's (2015), this method typically involves bringing together a group of individuals who share a common characteristic, facilitated by a researcher, to engage in group interactions, exchange perspectives on a specific topic, discuss personal experiences, and provide suggestions. It's important to note that the methodology of focus group research explicitly emphasizes the use of interaction. The discussions took in face-to-face.

Furthermore, in-depth or one-on-one interviews were also conducted to provide valuable opportunity for exploring the perceptions of secondary students with regards to their vocabulary knowledge. Fourteen (14) students were purposively selected for these interviews, which was conducted by the researcher. The in-depth interviews were carried out in face-to-face form lasting for 20 to 30 minutes.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics such as the mean were utilized to assess the average responses of the respondents. Moreover, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and T-test were used to determine the significant difference in the Vocabulary Knowledge of the participants when grouped accord to their profile. The survey data, which was collected, served as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data was tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data was further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of secondary students.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Regarding the qualitative data analysis, the researcher employed coding and thematic analysis. This involved examining the patterns and themes that emerged from the utterances or statements of the participants/informants during the one-on-one and focus group interviews. The themes were formulated with the purpose of analyzing the perspectives of secondary students in understanding vocabulary knowledge. The data was carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the secondary students from Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect, and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews. During the conduct of my study, I established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. I also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants will have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Informed Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. By obtaining informed consent, the participants are made fully aware of the objectives and purpose of the research they are being asked to participate in. Written consent was obtained from the participants, certifying their approval to take part in the in-depth interviews and focused group discussions. They were provided with information about the results and findings of the study, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed (Creswell, 2012).

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, I provided the participants with letters of permission and consent that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate were allowed to leave without any explanations and were assured that their data would remain confidential. The researcher also informed the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher was able to ensure that the study was conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, I took steps to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' responses and personal identities. To minimize any potential risks, the interview was conducted inside the school premises and engage in face-to-face interactions with the participants. By taking these measures, I was able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices. Furthermore, the data collected from this research study was used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Meaning, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the participants' identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in

terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, I was able to protect the participants' identity and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants. Given that the study aimed to understand the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Secondary students were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phase. The first phase deals with the quantitative part, in which it displays the level of vocabulary knowledge among secondary students. The second phase deals with the qualitative part, in which it is presented in a matrix form. The matrix shows the responses of the participants to their perceptions with regards to their vocabulary knowledge. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Vocabulary Knowledge

Vocabulary Knowledge. Shown in Table 2 is the level of vocabulary knowledge among secondary students at Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao. It obtained an overall mean score of 11.40 with a description of low. This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge of secondary students is considered low. The variable of the study, which is vocabulary knowledge, has three indicators, namely: vocabulary form, vocabulary meaning, and vocabulary use.

Vocabulary Form. In terms of form, the category mean is 4.07, which is described as low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of form is low. The highest score is 8, which was obtained by 5 students which is described as high. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of form is considered high. On the other hand, the lowest score was 1, which was obtained by 4 students, which is described as very low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of form is considered very low.

Table 1.3. *Status of Vocabulary Knowledge of Secondary Students*

Indicators	Frequency	Mean	Description
A. Vocabulary Form			
1	4	4.07	This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of form is considered low
2	15		
3	15		
4	7		
5	7		
6	10		
7	5		
8	5		
Total	68		
B. Vocabulary Meaning			
0	1	4.06	This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of meaning is considered low
1	8		
2	13		
3	14		
4	4		
5	8		
6	6		
7	4		
8	10		
Total	68		
C. Vocabulary Use			
0	4	3.26	This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of use is considered low
1	7		
2	8		
3	22		
4	14		
5	3		
6	9		
8	1		
Total	68		
Overall Mean		11.40	Low

Vocabulary Meaning. The secondary students obtained a category mean of 4.06 under the vocabulary meaning, hence, described as

low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of meaning is considered low. Out of 10 items in this category, ten students got the highest score of 8, which is described as high. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of meaning is considered high. Conversely, one student got the lowest score of 0, which is described as very low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students is considered very low.

Vocabulary Use. The vocabulary use garnered a category mean of 3.26, thus, described as low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of use is considered low. Out of 10 items in the category, one student got the highest score of 8, which is described as high. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of use is considered high. Meanwhile, the lowest score is 0, obtained by 4 students, which is described as very low. This means that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in terms of use is considered very low.

The Perception of Secondary Students with Regards to Their Vocabulary Knowledge

There are four essential themes which were created based from in-depth interview and focus group discussion of the participants on the first research question. Before the presentation of the results from the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative data collection are presented in table 1.2. The table represents the participants' profiles for the qualitative phases were selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a grade 10 student currently enrolled in Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao. Based on the table, the profile is divided into two categories, seven (7) participants for in-depth interview and another seven (7) for focus group discussion.

Further, Table 2 emphasized the perception of secondary students with regards to their vocabulary knowledge. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for the research question number one are consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Psychological Factors. In the context of vocabulary knowledge, the psychological factors pertain to the emotions, interest, motivation, and attitudes of the secondary students that influence them towards vocabulary learning as support for emotional satisfaction and confidence in vocabulary development as well as, motivational barriers in vocabulary learning. It was mentioned by the participants that the psychological factors are what influence them to learn new words.

Table 2. *The Perception of Secondary Students with Regards to their Vocabulary Knowledge*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Framework</i>
The Impact of Motivational Factors to Student's Vocabulary Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeling proud and satisfied with oneself when learning new words Being confident in having an advanced vocabulary Feeling happy and amazed with oneself when understanding a certain word Having a sense of discouragement when learning English words due to fear of grammatical errors Finding English as boring prevents students' interest in learning new words Being negligent or lacking self-motivation towards vocabulary learning 	Emotional Satisfaction and Confidence in Vocabulary Development Motivational Barriers in Vocabulary Learning	Psychological Factors	Self-Determination Theory (SDT)
The Negative Impact on Vocabulary Learning Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being unable to comprehend words with deeper meanings Encountering unfamiliar words while reading The difficulties on retaining and familiarizing new words Difficulties on the pronunciation of words Incorrect spelling of words Confusion with the functions of parts of speech in sentence Difficulties in identifying the synonym and antonym of words 	Difficulties in Vocabulary Comprehension Difficulties in Vocabulary Formation	Challenges Towards Vocabulary Learning	Word Recognition Theory
Challenges in Assessing Proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehending new words easier due to having a wider vocabulary 	Students with High or Neutral Vocabulary Knowledge	Vocabulary Proficiency Level	Vocabulary Depth Theory

- Students having a neutral vocabulary knowledge as while undergoing in the learning process
 - Having a neutral knowledge level in vocabularies in catching up with the lessons
 - Unable to comprehend teacher's discussion due to having a low vocabulary knowledge level
 - Students with insufficient vocabulary are unable to comprehend basic words
 - Majority of students have low vocabulary knowledge level due to intrinsic factors
- Students with Low Vocabulary knowledge Level

Emotional Satisfaction and Confidence in Vocabulary Development. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Students expressed common responses in terms of the emotional satisfaction and the confidence they feel upon learning new words. Most of them stated that learning new words can boost their self-confidence and emotional satisfaction.

"Ma happy og ma proud ko sa'kong sarili kay at least in a day naa koy natun-an nga new word that I know na beneficial para sa akoo labi na gyud nga naa pa ko sa phase nga gatuon pa lang. So, para nako kay ma consider na nako siya as an achievement." (IDI-06)

(I feel proud of myself because at least a day I have a new learned word that I know beneficial for me, especially right now wherein I am still in the learning phase. So, for me, I can consider it as an achievement.)

Moreover, learning new words helps the students to feel motivated and confident inside the classroom setting. By learning new words, a student may feel more advance among other students. It is clear that the students' confidence is boost when there is a vocabulary development. As what Zya said that:

"Akong ma feel kung makatuon ko 'g mga new words kay motivated and confident kay nadungagan na akong kaalam. Og kung sa klase morag ma advance na ko kung mo tubag kung naay mga new words nga wala sila kabalo unya ako kay kabalo na ko." (FGD-06)

(What I feel when I learned new words is motivated and confident because I gained more knowledge. And inside the class is that I feel quite advance when answering if I know the words while others won't.)

In addition, students claimed that there are still words they don't know yet, that's why students feel happy when they learned a certain word. By learning new words, students are able to teach other students who are unable to understand the word. Hence, highlighting the satisfaction that students feel when they are able to understand a certain word. As Leo stated that:

"Pag naa koy nahibal-an nga words kay malipay ko kay as a student daghan pa ko 'g wala nahibal-an nga mga words unya pag makabalo ko kay malipay ko kay pwede pud nako siya itudlo sa lain kung di pud nila na masabtan nga word." (FGD-07)

(When I learned new words is that I feel happy because as a student there are many words that I still don't know yet, that's why I feel happy because I can teach it to others if they are unable to understand the word as well.)

Motivational Barriers in Vocabulary Learning. This is the second code of the first probed issue. IDI and FGD participants imparted that motivational barriers affect their vocabulary learning. Commonly, the secondary students shared that they feel less likely to learn new words when they are not motivated or interested. As a result, students are discouraged to learning new words, in particular, the English.

In that sense, what hinders the student's vocabulary knowledge is being uninterested or not fond in English. Also, the students may feel discouraged to learn English words due to being afraid of committing grammatical errors. As a result, students' motivation towards vocabulary learning particularly in English is impeded. Similarly, Jes said that:

"Ang maka hinder pud sa akoo since ge ingon na nako nga dili kayu nako bet ang English kay dili pud ko ingon nga hawud kaayu ana. Unya permente pud ko ma wrong sa'kong grammar, siguro mao na ang isa nga maka pa discourage sa akoo mag learn og English og since dili pud ko interesado ana." (IDI-01)

(One thing that hinders me is being not fond in English since I am not really good at it. And I often commit grammatical errors, maybe it is something that discourages me to learn English, since I am also not interested about it.)

Moreover, if students find English as boring, then the lesser the chance that they would learn new words. As such, students become lazy towards vocabulary learning. Zya said that:

"Ang maka hinder sad sa amo mga students nga makatuon kay kanang feeling nila boring ang English maong tamaron sila mag tuon og new words." (FGD-06)

(What hinders us, we, the students to learn is that when we feel that English is boring, that's why we feel lazy to learn new words.)

In addition, enhancing one's vocabulary knowledge depends on the students' interest. Basically, what prevents student's vocabulary learning is their negligence to learn or having lack of self-motivation. As Joy said that:

"Makasulti ko nga mag depende pud gyud na sa interest sa usa ka student ang pag enhance sa iyang vocabulary knowledge og I think po nga ang maka hinder pud sa bata nga maka tuon is kanang walay pakialam sa pagtuon or kulang og self-motivation." (FGD-07)

(I could say that it depends on the interest of the student to enhance his vocabulary and I think that what hinders the student to learn is being negligent to learn or having lack of self-motivation.)

Challenges Towards Vocabulary Learning. Students are persistent to learn new words, however along with the vocabulary learning process, secondary students often faced challenges based from the similar responses given by the participants. Based on the information gathered from the participants' responses is that they shared commonalities of how these challenges affect their vocabulary skills.

Difficulties in Vocabulary Comprehension. This is the first code of the second probed issue. The students shared that understanding the meaning of word is one the challenges they faced when encountering new words. This barrier impedes students' ability to effectively understand and learn the words.

In connection to this, Participant 1 explained that there are times wherein she was unable to comprehend the words she found from the stories as part of the activity set by the teacher, due to unfamiliarity of words or having no knowledge about the words. As well as, there are taglines in the story wherein she barely understands. But still, she seeks out opportunities to learn the words anent to her curiosity. She stated that:

"If mag hatag og mga activities ang mga teachers like for example mga stories, naay mga unfamiliar words nga dili nako masabtan or wala koy knowledge ato nga words. Kana pong naay mga tagline naay mga words ana ma'am nga dili nako siya masabtan. So, ma curious ko og ako na siyang tun-an." (IDI-01)

(If the teacher will give an activity like for example, stories. There are unfamiliar words I could not comprehend or I have no knowledge about those words. Also, when there are taglines, there are words from it that I could not comprehend. So, I got curious and learn it.)

Moreover, Bea stated that she encountered numerous challenges when learning about vocabularies. And one of her biggest challenges is the unfamiliarity of words which hinders her vocabulary comprehension. Also, she faced difficulties in terms of word pronunciation and use, specifically on how to use the word whether in writing or speaking. Hence, it highlights the barriers that she encountered in terms of vocabulary. Bea said that:

"Honestly, daghan gyud kayu ko'g challenges nga ma encounter the moment nga mag tuon ko about vocabularies. Una na diraa is kanang unfamiliar words, mao gyud na akong biggest challenge kay pag once man gud ang word nga imong mabasa or madungog nga bag o sa imoha is dili gyud malikayan nga dili ka kasabot unsay gina mean ana so mahimo gyud siyang hindrance sa akong word comprehension. Og ikaduha, usahay mag lisod gyud ko'g pronounce sa mga words nga bag-o pa nako na encounter as well as kung unsaon siya pag gamit either in writing or speaking." (FGD-04)

(Honestly, there are many challenges I encounter the moment I learn about vocabulary. First and foremost is the unfamiliar words, it is really my biggest challenge since hearing or reading a words that are new to me is that it's really inevitable that it hinders my word comprehension. Secondly, sometimes, I hardly pronounce the words that I just newly encountered, as well as, how it is use either in writing or speaking.)

In addition, secondary students faced difficulties on recalling and familiarizing the words. Students struggle of recalling the words they have previously learned due to issues with memory retention or retrieval. As well as, in familiarizing new words in terms of understanding its meaning. As what Zya stated that:

"Ang mga challenges na ko kanang dali ra malimtan labi na ang mga words jud nga dili familiar unya tag-as kaayu og mga meaning unya pagkasunod adlaw kay malimtan na nimo kung unsay meaning ato kay naa napud kay mabasa nga mga new words." (FGD-06)

(My challenges is that, I forgot easily the words that are not really familiar and have lengthy meaning, then, on the next day, you forgotten its meaning because you have read another new words.)

Difficulties in Vocabulary Formation. This is the second code for the second probed issue. shared their common responses with regards to the challenges they faced in understanding the relationships of words. Students struggle to grasp the meanings of these new words, leading to difficulties in expressing themselves effectively. Additionally, learning synonyms and antonyms can be challenging due to the nuances and subtle differences in meaning between words. This can affect students' ability to use language accurately and appropriately in different contexts.

In connection to that, students stated that one of the challenges they often encountered was the pronunciation of a certain word when learning new vocabulary. This can be due to unfamiliarity and complexity of the words. Jes explained that:

"The common challenge nga akong ma encounter is about sa pronunciation sa isa ka word nga dili familiar sa akoo or kanang lisod"

e pronounce nga word." (IDI-01)

(The common challenge I often encountered is about the pronunciation of a certain word that is unfamiliar or complex word to utter.)

Moreover, Amy said that students face difficulties in spelling out the word. English spelling can be particularly tricky because many words are naturally complex that can be confusing for learners that might affect student's academic performance. She said that:

"Kanang kapila na ko ka beses mamali sa mga activities nga ihatag ni teacher labi na kung mag pa spelling gamay ra kayu ko'g score kay mag libog ko usahay gyud sa mga letters labi na tong mga words nga laglom gyud kaayu." (IDI-03)

(I was mistaken multiple times during the activities set by the teacher particularly in spelling, I got low score because sometimes I got confused with the letters especially with those complex words.)

Furthermore, Mia mentioned that often she faced difficulties with grammar as she navigates language learning. When she encountered unfamiliar vocabulary, she struggles to construct grammatically correct sentences using these new words. For example, using the correct tense, verb form, or sentence structure with newly learned vocabulary can be challenging. Conversely, difficulties with grammar can impede students' ability to accurately use and comprehend vocabulary in context. As what Mia said that:

"Para nako hangtud karon mag lisod gihapon ko sa grammar labi na gyud sa functions sa mga verbs, past and present tenses. Maong most of the time, daghan ko'g corrections kung mag buhat mi'g essay." (FGD-01)

(For me, until now I struggle with grammar most especially in terms with the functions of verbs, past and present tenses. That's why, most of the time, I got corrections when writing an essay.)

Lastly, Bea shared that she struggled in identifying the synonyms and antonyms a certain word which hinders her from comprehending the word effectively. This highlights the challenges faced by the students in terms of vocabulary formation when learning new vocabulary.

"Right now, ang challenge nga ma encounter na ko in terms sa pag learn sa vocabulary kay about sa kung unsay synonym or antonym sa usa ka word. For example, mag basa ko'g books unya kung naa koy ma encounter nga word nga unfamiliar gina search nako tapos mahibaw-an nalang nako nga mao ra diay pasabot ato, it's just that ge ilisan siya'g lahi nga word pero mao rang pasabota." (FGD-04)

(Right now, the challenge I encountered in terms of learning vocabulary is about the synonym and antonym of a certain word. For example, when I read books and encountered words that are unfamiliar then searched it, then later found out that the word meant it, it's just that, it was replaced with another word but just means the same.)

Vocabulary Proficiency Level. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the categories of students with high or neutral vocabulary knowledge and students with low vocabulary knowledge level. The participants shared a common response with regards to their perceptions to students' vocabulary knowledge level. They stated that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students can vary widely from individual to individual. While some secondary students may have an average vocabulary knowledge, others may demonstrate exceptional proficiency or struggle with vocabulary acquisition.

Students with High or Neutral Vocabulary Knowledge. This is the first code of the third probed issue. In-depth interview and FGD participants imparted their perceptions in terms of their vocabulary proficiency levels. Focusing to what extent do they can assess the level of their vocabulary knowledge as a secondary student.

Consequently, secondary students believe that they gained a wider vocabulary knowledge as they encountered a broader range of vocabularies along with their progress through school. Typically, secondary students have a wider or neutral vocabulary as compared to the younger students, due to their increased exposure to language through formal education. As what Jes said that:

"I believe nga ang secondary students kay daghan na sila 'g knowledge about sa vocabulary og mas dali nila matun.an ang mga words since naa na man sila sa higher level sa pag skwela." (IDI-01)

(I believe that the secondary students have gained more knowledge about vocabulary and it's easier for them to learn the words since they are already in higher level of schooling.)

Moreover, Liz stated that her perception towards to secondary students' vocabulary knowledge is that they just have an average vocabulary range as they are still in the learning phase, particularly in English language. This highlights the idea that some secondary students have a neutral vocabulary knowledge level. She said that:

"As a secondary student particularly grade 10, one thing I could say or my perception sa usa ka vocabulary sa students is kanang dili pa kaayu wide ilahang vocabulary unya dili pud kaayu ubos naa ra sila sa tama-tama because we are still learning particularly sa English language." (IDI-02)

(As a secondary student, particularly, grade 10, one thing I could say or my perception towards the students' vocabularies is that their

vocabularies are not totally wide and not so low, just an average because they are still learning particularly in English language.)

Lastly, Sue shared her perception which she states her observation towards her classmates. She said that her classmates' vocabulary knowledge level is just average as they were able to catch-up the lesson in class discussions while others were not really paying attention with the lesson or unable to understand the lesson. These students basically seek support from their teacher's assistance for them to be able to understand the lesson, particularly in English or Filipino. As Sue said that:

“Ang akong panan-aw sa’kong mga classmates is kaning middle pa lang ang among level of vocabulary. Naay uban nakong mga classmates nga makasabot na sila sa lesson tapos ang mga uban kanang dili pa sila mo pay attention sa mga lessons or wala pa silay nasabtan like ang teacher pa ang mo make way para makasabot sila ma’am like sa English or Filipino.” (IDI-05)

(My perception towards my classmates is that, the level of our vocabulary is in middle. Some of my classmates were already able to catch-up with the lesson while others were not paying attention with the lessons or unable to learn something, like the teacher is the one who makes a way for them to learn like in English or Filipino.)

Students with Low Vocabulary Knowledge Level. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants shared that some secondary students may have an average or even-above average vocabulary level while others may have poor or low vocabulary level. They have observed that students with limited vocabulary tend to have a poor vocabulary comprehension skill.

Similar to that, students observed that the secondary students enrolled at their school have a low vocabulary, based from the students' observation among their classmates. Most of the students barely understood the lessons being taught to them. Also, students with low vocabulary were unable to learn independently and need to be guided by the teacher for them to understand the lesson. As Amy said that:

“In my observation about the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students especially in Saint Jude is kanang low gyud ilahang vocabulary labi na gyud sa akong mga classmates, mag lisod pa sila og sabot kung unsa ang mga gina tudlo sa ilaha. Ang teacher pa ang ga make way para masabtan nila. Example pud is sa akoo, dili pud kaayu ko taas og comprehension and gamay pud gyud ko og vocabulary.” (IDI-03)

(In my observation about the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students especially in Saint Jude is that their vocabularies are low most especially, my classmates, they hardly understand the teachings that taught to them. It's the teacher who make a way for their understanding. Example is myself, my comprehension is quite high and my vocabulary is just limited.)

Similarly, students observed that some students have deeper vocabulary knowledge levels or fluent with word pronunciation and comprehension. At there are also students who hardly comprehend even with the basic words or terminologies. This highlights the effect of having a low or limited vocabulary knowledge among secondary students.

“On what I have observed, is naay mga secondary students nga lalom ilang vocabulary knowledge or hawd sila sa pronunciation, comprehension and at the same time naa say mga students nga galisod og sabot sa a bisan basic lang nga mga terms sa vocabulary.” (IDI-04)

(On what I have observed is there are secondary students who have deeper vocabulary knowledge or fluent in pronunciation and comprehension. And at the same time, there are students who hardly comprehend even with the basic words or terminologies.)

Lastly, Roy observed that majority of the secondary students have low vocabulary knowledge than those with high vocabulary knowledge. This was subjected to students' attitudes and misbehavior that prevents students to learn vocabulary. He explained that:

“Mas daghan ang naay low vocabulary knowledge kaysa sa taas og vocabulary knowledge kay ang reason ana kung ngano, kay mas gamay ra’g gapaningkamot og mas daghag badlungon.” (IDI-07)

(Majority have low vocabulary knowledge than those with high vocabulary knowledge because the reason why is that, fewer students strive and majority are mischievous.)

The Insights of Secondary Students with Regards to Vocabulary Knowledge

Displayed in Table 3.1 were the responses of the participants with regards to their insights to secondary students' vocabulary knowledge. There were four essential themes which were drawn out from the in-depth and focus group discussion of the participants for the second question. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table.

Dynamic Language Enrichment. The insights of secondary students in accordance to their vocabulary knowledge are being affected based from the similar responses given by the participants. Based from the information shared by the participants, it is claimed that there are variety of instructional techniques and activities designed to enhance students' vocabulary skills through engaging and interactive means. Recognizing the importance of how these dynamic language enrichment enrich students' vocabulary knowledge.

Maximizing Language Interaction and Exposure. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Secondary students suggest that teachers should maximized language interaction and exposure where students have dynamic opportunities to engage with language in various contexts and interact with others using rich vocabulary. Students recognized that this approach is crucial for enhancing students'

vocabulary knowledge because it allows them to experience language in authentic and meaningful ways, leading to a deeper understanding and retention of vocabulary.

Table 3.1. *The Insights of Secondary Students with Regards to their Vocabulary Knowledge*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Framework</i>
The Impact of Sources of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating interactive activities relevant to vocabulary learning Engage students in reading and writing activities Being resourceful to activate learners' participation Providing support to students in enhancing their vocabulary knowledge Providing students with opportunity to speak English during English period Watching educational videos through online platforms relative to vocabulary Spending time to have an access to available resources in the library Learning new words through dictionary and google Training oneself to keep on learning new words through constant reading on English books 	Maximizing Language Interaction and Exposure Utilizing Accessible Resources for Vocabulary Expansion	Dynamic Language Enrichment	Vocabulary Exposure Theory
Impact of Vocabulary Knowledge on Classroom Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vocabulary improves all forms of communication such as reading, writing, listening and speaking Fosters students' ability to answer oral recitations efficiently Obtaining high scores in exams Wider vocabularies favor students achieved academic excellence achievement Establishing vocabulary skills for future academic endeavors Being open for adapting new vocabularies for self-preparedness Developing one's vocabulary knowledge to foster vocabulary comprehension 	Enhanced Classroom Participation and Engagement Vocabulary Development for Academic Endeavors	Enhanced Academic Performance	Strategic Investment Theory
Contextual Appropriateness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning new words to know how it is used in a specific context Learning new words to understand how it is applied in a sentence Learning new words to form grammatical structure Learning new words for comprehending academic instructions Determining self-progress through vocabulary attainment Imparting knowledge in vocabularies towards others 	Vocabulary Usage Vocabulary Progress	Vocabulary Knowledge Advancement	Usage-Based Theory

Similarly, students suggest that their English teachers should integrate interactive activities in delivering the lessons. As they believe that integrating interactive activities into discussions can enhance student's engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes by providing a dynamic and stimulating learning environment. By keeping students actively involved and interested in the topic, interactive activities can help prevent boredom and foster a deeper understanding of vocabulary concepts. As what Zya recommended that:

“Ang ma recommend nako sa among English teacher kay pwede nila ipaagi sa activities ilang pag tudlo kay ang ubang students man gud kay mas ganahan sila maminaw kung ang maestra dili gud boring mo tudlo like ginahimo bitaw nilang dula-dula pero naa gihapoy kalabutan sa leksyon.” (FGD-06)

(What I can recommend to our English teacher is they can deliver their teachings through activities because some students more likely to listen if the teacher's class delivery is not boring, like they make learning fun, but still connected in the lesson.)

Similar to that, students must engage with reading and writing activities, particularly, spelling. As well as, students recognized the importance of spending time in English lessons. This highlights the importance of reading and writing as an effective effective way to provide students with language interaction and exposure.

Roy suggested that:

"Akong ma recommend sa mga teachers kay mag pabasa sila sa nga students og e apply nila ang mga activities like spelling og mag hatag gyud og time sa English lesson." (IDI-07)

(What I can recommend to my teachers is to allow students read and apply an activities like spelling and spend time for English lesson.)

Moreover, students advised teachers to incorporate other resources that best suit students' interest while engaging in class discussions. Because students tend to learn better when they find learning enjoyable and engaging. When learning is fun, students are more motivated, attentive, and likely to retain information. Through this, students will be more exposed to language interactions. As Ann said that:

"Advice nako sa teachers is since they are the ones who will be teaching kids kay promote other resources kung asa mas ma inganyo ang students maminaw, the more na active sila the more pud nga mag participate sila sa klase which is pinaagi ana nag enjoy na sila, nakatuon pa sila." (FGD-05)

(My advice to the teachers is since they are the ones who will be teaching kids, is promote other resources to which students will more likely listen, the more they are active, the more they will participate in class which is through that way, apart from enjoying, they learned as well.)

Additionally, what enriches students' vocabulary knowledge is when teacher provides support to students especially those with low vocabulary knowledge level. Teacher should motivate the students to learn to better enhance their vocabularies. Highlighting the importance of teacher's support for students' vocabulary development. Amy recommended that:

"Akong ma recommend sa among English teachers is dapat hatagan gyud nilag pag tagad ang mga students labi na gyud tong low pa gyud og vocabulary level og ilang e motivate nga mag tuon pa gyud aron ma enhance pagyud ilang vocabularies." (IDI-03)

(My recommendation to our English teachers is to provide attention to students especially those who have low vocabulary level and motivate them to learn more to enhance their vocabularies better.)

Lastly, Bea suggested the importance of providing students with opportunities to practice their selves using vocabulary context. He stated that, this approach is very effective where students were able to interact using the English language which encourages them to strive to learn vocabularies. This highlights the importance of language interaction and exposure among secondary students. She mentioned that:

"Since sa among school kay wala kayu namo ni siya gina put into practice so, akong ma advice sa 'kong English teachers nga e allow gyud nila ang mga students nga mag English during English period kay para nako effective gyud kayu ni siya nga pamaagi para ang mga students kay maningkamot gyud og tuon about vocabularies." (FGD-04)

(Since in our school is that we are not totally putting it into practice, so my advice to my English teachers is to allow the students speak English during English period, because for me, this is very effective way for students to strive to learn about vocabularies.)

Utilizing Accessible Resources for Vocabulary Expansion. This is the second code for the first probed issue. Participants offered their takeaways to secondary students with regards to expanding their vocabularies. When learning new words, students recognized the importance of utilizing accessible resources such as books, educational apps, and online platforms which provide students with diverse opportunities to encounter new words in different contexts. By engaging with these resources students can expand their vocabulary, improve their comprehension skills and enhance their overall language proficiency.

In connection to that, in order for a student to expand their vocabulary knowledge, it's advisable to watch educational videos related to vocabulary learning via social media platforms. Through this way, students will be provided with dynamic and accessible resources that support students' vocabulary expansion. As Mia stated that:

"If hatagan ko'g chance, ingnon na ko sila nga mag try sila og tan-aw sa tiktok or any social media platforms that talks about vocabulary. Try to search it pud kay beneficial kaayu siya para sa iyang kaugalingon." (FGD-01)

(If I'll be given a chance, I would tell them to try watching tiktok or any other social media platforms that talk about vocabulary. Also, try to search it as it is so beneficial for themselves.)

Aside from that, it was advised by the participants that students should spend time to go to the library to have an access to available resources, especially those with low vocabulary knowledge level. Participants reasoned that library offers a wide range of books and

other written materials. By exploring these resources, students encountered new words which can contribute to students' vocabulary expansion. She said that:

“Ang ako lang maingon sa mga other students nga low vocabulary level kay as long as gusto nila and willing sila maka learn pwede sila mag adtu sa library para mag basa og mga books para naa silay ma learn about sa vocabulary.” (FGD-04)

(What I can say with the other students with low vocabulary level is that as long as they wanted and willing to learn, they can go to the library to read books so they can learn something about vocabulary.)

In addition, it is valuable to secondary students to train their selves to keep learning new words through constant reading and continue study harder. Through this ways, students can expand their vocabularies as they encountered different words from what they have read. This also allows students understand the meaning of unfamiliar words they encountered. As what Mia stated that:

“Akoa lang maingon sa ilaha is study hard, mag basa perme para ma improve og para daghan ta'g unfamiliar words nga masabtan na nato.” (FGD-01)

(What I can tell them is study hard, read oftentimes for improvement and for us to have numerous understanding with the unfamiliar words.)

Enhanced Academic Performance. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the categories of enhanced classroom participation and engagement and vocabulary development for academic endeavors. The participants mentioned how students' vocabulary knowledge enhanced their academic performance. Students with better vocabulary knowledge tend to excel academically. These students are better equipped to grasp academic texts, communicate effectively in writing and speaking, and express themselves clearly in academic context.

Enhanced Classroom Participation and Engagement. This is the first code of the second probed issue. In-depth interview and FGD participants imparted the importance students' vocabulary knowledge towards their academic performance. They shared their insights how their vocabularies helped them enhance classroom participation and engagement.

Consequently, students recognized the importance of vocabulary, as it improves all forms of communication such as listening, speaking, writing and reading. Students expressed that vocabulary is critical in every child's success and academic achievement. This highlights the idea that vocabulary knowledge can significantly elevate the quality and effectiveness of communication across various contexts and mediums. Tom stated that:

“Importante jud kaayu ang vocabulary sa akoo because it improves all areas of communication—listening, speaking, reading and writing. Vocabulary is critical for child's success and academic achievement.” (FGD-02)

(Vocabulary is very important for me, because it improves all areas of communication—listening, speaking, reading and writing. Vocabulary is critical for child's success and academic achievement.)

Apparently, having an advance vocabulary basically allows students articulate their thoughts precisely and formulate opinions when answering academic questions. With an extensive vocabulary, students can better understand academic texts, analyze information critically, and develop insightful interpretations. As what Zya said that:

“In terms of academic, importante kaayu among vocabulary kay kung mas advance ang amoang mga nahibal-an mas daghan mi'g mga ideas or opinions nga matubag sa klase especially sa mga orals or exams.” (FGD-06)

(In terms of academic, our vocabularies really matter because when we have some more advance learnings, the better we have ideas or opinions in answering in the class especially in orals or exams.)

Furthermore, in academic context, students stated that having sufficient vocabularies are crucial for obtaining high scores in exams. Because this made easier for students to understand written texts. Amy stated that:

“Para sa akoo importante jud ang vocabularies sa academic kay the more nga daghan ka'g nahibal-an nga words maka gain gyud ka'g high scores sa exams.” (IDI-03)

(For me, vocabulary is really important in academic because the more you have many known words, you can gain high scores in exams.)

Lastly, students valued the importance of vocabulary because this helped students achieved academic excellence easier. Allowing students understand words with unfamiliarity. This highlights the significance of gaining vocabulary for uplifting students' academic success and learning outcomes. He said that:

“Para sa akoo kay importante kaayu ang vocabulary sa academic kay kung naa kay nabil-an sa vocabulary dali na lang para sa imoha mahimong academic achiever kay naa na man kay nahibaw-an about sa vocabulary. Dali na lang ka makasabot sa mga dili kayu familiar nga mga words sa imoha.” (FGD-03)

(For me, vocabulary is very important in academic because when you have knowledge in vocabulary, it made easier for you to be an academic achiever because you already have knowledge about vocabulary. It is easier for you to understand words that are quite unfamiliar.)

Vocabulary Development for Academic Endeavors. This is the second code for the second probed issue. As students' progress into higher levels of education, they encounter more sophisticated texts and concepts that require a robust vocabulary for comprehension and analysis. Additionally, a strong vocabulary is valuable for student's academic preparedness in terms of vocabulary understanding. Participants have mentioned that investing in vocabulary development during secondary school lays a solid foundation for future academic endeavors.

Similar to that, learning about English vocabulary is very crucial for grade 10 students for their future academic endeavors. Students have to be facilitated as they move through with the learning process. As such, they became more prepared when encountering unfamiliar words as they proceed to senior high or college era. As what Jes stated that:

"As a grade 10 student, importante ni siya para sa amoa para next school year kay mag senior high naman mi para mas ready na mi po maka encounter og unfamiliar words. Maong sa karon pa lang dapat mas ma encourage mi or ma motivate mi nga mag learn more about English or vocabulary kay para next school year ready na mi mag learn og another word." (IDI-01)

(As a grade 10 student, it is important to us for the next school year since we will proceed to senior high, for us to be ready when encountering unfamiliar words. That's why right now, we have to be more encouraged or motivated to learn about English or vocabulary so that for the next school year, we are ready to learn another word.)

Furthermore, Zya said that adapting new vocabulary skills is crucial for preparing their selves for higher schooling. Students acknowledge the importance of vocabulary knowledge in preparing oneself for future academic endeavors. Zya stated that:

"Akong masulti kay dapat jud nga open mi nga makatuon og maka adapt og mga bag-ong skills sa among mga vocabulary knowledge og aron ma prepare namo among sarili pag abot namo sa higher level." (FGD-06)

(I can say that we really have to be open for learning and adapting new skills in our vocabulary knowledge and to prepare our selves for higher level.)

Lastly, students have to improve their vocabulary skills in earlier grade level. As it provides the students an opportunity to deepen and widen their vocabularies. Participants mentioned that students with academic preparedness tend to foster vocabulary comprehension. He said that:

"Para sa akong masulti kay dapat since grade 7 pa lang ka is mag study na gyud ka about sa vocabularies kay para pag tong-tong nimo sa grade 10 kay taas-taas na ka'g knowledge og daku-daku na imong nahibal-an about vocabularies." (FGD-03)

(What I can say is that, since grade 7 is that you have to study about vocabularies so that when you reach grade 10 is that you already acquired higher knowledge and wider understanding about vocabularies.)

Vocabulary Knowledge Advancement. The participants provided their insights with regards to their vocabulary progress. Developmental progress in vocabulary knowledge refers to the growth and advancement in a students' understanding and use of words over time. This progression typically occurs as individuals learn new words, their meanings, and how to use them in various contexts.

Vocabulary Usage. This is the first code of the third probed issue. Participants stated that is important that they know and understand the use of words within specific contexts or situations. It involves recognizing how words are used in sentences, paragraphs, or conversations to convey meaning effectively. By understanding the context in which a word is used, individuals can better grasp its meaning and apply it accurately in their own language use.

Consequently, Kim recognized the importance of not just knowing the meaning of words but also how it is used in a certain context. In essence, understanding how a word is used in context enhances language comprehension. This highlights the significance of contextualization. As what Kim stated that:

"For me is kanang dili lang mi dapat makabalo'g new words but kanang unsaon pud nga maka improve siya sa'tong understanding og kanang unsaon pag gamit sa word." (IDI-06)

(For me is that, it's not enough to only know the words but also how it can improve our understanding and how the word is used.)

Similarly, students claimed that it's important that you are aware of how a certain word is used in context. Also, it's crucial to have knowledge on vocabulary particularly the definition. By this, students will be able to know how a specific word is structurally used in a sentence. She claimed that:

"Ang lesson nga akong natun-an is naa koy mga words nga kabalo na ko para asa siya angay gamiton. Importante man gud nga kabalo ka sa word og sa iyang definition para mas han-ay imohang sentence." (FGD-05)

(The lesson I've learned is that I have known words that I know where it is appropriately used. Because it is important that I know the

word from its definition for you to construct a sentence better.)

Lastly, Tom stated that students should develop their vocabulary knowledge. Developing students' vocabulary is beneficial for grammatical and sentence structure. This emphasizes the importance of vocabulary knowledge for applying the words linguistically. As what Tom said that:

"Akoa lang masulti kay need gyud nato e expand atong vocabulary knowledge kay magamit nato ni siya like for example mag buhat ta og grammar or mga sentences." (FGD-02)

(What I can say is we need to expand our vocabulary knowledge because it is useful like for example, constructing grammar or other sentences.)

Vocabulary Progress. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants mentioned that vocabulary learning, vocabulary attainment and vocabulary comprehension are determined through students' vocabulary progress. In connection to that, students explained that in academic context, vocabulary knowledge serves as a foundation for academic success by enhancing students' ability to comprehend, interpret, and apply academic instructions across various subject areas. It empowers students to engage more effectively with academic content and tasks, ultimately supporting their overall learning and achievement. As what Kim said that:

"Importante siya sa akoa like for example sa academic, as a with honors kanang mag hatag og tasks among maestra kay dili na kayu ko mag lisod og kanang sabot sa instructions." (IDI-06)

(It's very important for me like for example in academic, as a with honors is that if our teacher gives tasks, it's easier for me to understand the instructions.)

Moreover, the lesson that the students learned with regards to vocabulary knowledge is that a student's vocabulary progress is determined based from the mental and personal development of the students. Because if students progress mentally, then the wider the vocabulary knowledge they've learned. And for personal development, if students are able to communicate effectively then that proves the students' vocabulary progress. As Zya stated that:

"Ang lessons nga akong natun.an kay kinahanglan gyud kaayu namo nga ma expand among vocabularies kay dira sad ma determine ang mental and personal development sa usa ka student towards sa iyang pag skwela." (FGD-06)

(The lesson I have learned is we really need to expand our vocabularies because by this means, the mental and personal development of a student towards his study is determined.)

In addition, a student with rich vocabulary are often better equipped to impart knowledge to others. Then he is able to impart knowledge to others especially those students who struggle with word comprehension. With this, it highlights the students' vocabulary progress through sharing vocabulary knowledge towards others. She mentioned that:

"Importante kung wide ta'g vocabulary kay sa kini nga paagi pwede ta maka impart og knowledge pud sa uban nga nag lisod labi na gyud sa pag sabot sa mga words." (FGD-07)

(It is important when we have wide vocabulary. Because through this, we can also impart our knowledge to others particularly those who struggle with comprehending the words.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Data Findings

The present study on understanding the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students in a local private school carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The fourth research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 4 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect for focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in preceding columns.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. In the quantitative phase, the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students is considered as low. This result is connected with the qualitative findings: students with low vocabulary knowledge level, which is themed as vocabulary proficiency level. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. In the quantitative phase, the vocabulary form of secondary students is also rated as low. This result is connected to the qualitative findings: difficulties in vocabulary formation under the theme of challenges towards vocabulary learning. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitatively in this aspect.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. In the quantitative phase, the vocabulary meaning of secondary students is evaluated as low. This result is connected with the qualitative findings: difficulties in vocabulary comprehension, which are under the theme of challenges towards vocabulary learning. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with the with the quantitative.

Table 3.2. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect For Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Students' Vocabulary Knowledge	From Table 1.1 on vocabulary knowledge (M= 11.40) which considered as low.	Table 3.1 students with low vocabulary knowledge level under the theme of vocabulary proficiency level	Merging-Converging	Students assessed the level of their vocabulary knowledge as low in terms of vocabulary proficiency.
	From Table 1.1 on vocabulary form (M= 4.07) which considered as low.	Table 3.1 on difficulties in vocabulary formation under the theme of challenges towards vocabulary learning	Merging-Converging	Difficulties in vocabulary formation are one of the challenges faced by students in vocabulary learning.
	From Table 1.1 on vocabulary meaning (M= 4.06) which considered as low.	Table 3.1 on difficulties in vocabulary comprehension under the theme of challenges towards vocabulary learning	Merging-Converging	Difficulties in vocabulary comprehension are also one of the challenges faced by students towards vocabulary learning.
	From Table 1.1 on vocabulary use (M= 3.26) which considered as low.	Table 3.1 on vocabulary usage under the theme of vocabulary knowledge advancement	Merging-Converging	Vocabulary knowledge is determined by the students as a significant factor in enhancing their vocabulary knowledge
	From Table 1.1 on vocabulary use (M= 3.26) which considered as low.	Table 3.1 on enhanced classroom participation and engagement under the theme of enhanced academic performance	Merging-diverging	Students with low vocabulary use levels acknowledge the importance of enhancing one's vocabulary to better excel academically.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. The vocabulary use of secondary students is indicated as low in the quantitative phase. This result is connected with the qualitative findings: vocabulary usage, which is under the theme of vocabulary knowledge advancement. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with the with the quantitative .

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. In the quantitative phase of the study, secondary students were found to have limited vocabulary use. However, this finding contrasts with the qualitative results, which highlighted increased classroom participation and engagement under the theme of enhanced academic performance. Therefore, there is a discrepancy between the quantitative and qualitative data in this regard.

Status of Vocabulary Knowledge

The interpretation of the quantitative data generated from the survey is discussed here. Scholarly works and findings are utilized and cited to support the results of the study. This is done in order to have a robust analysis of the data.

Vocabulary Knowledge. As shown in the chapter 3, the overall level of Vocabulary Knowledge of Secondary Students is low. This result is indicative that the vocabulary knowledge level of secondary students is low. This is in congruence with the study of Afzal (2019) emphasizes that vocabulary, together with phonetics/pronunciation and grammar, is one of the most important components of learning a mother tongue or a foreign language. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are all built on the foundation of vocabulary. Learning the vocabulary is essential for achieving any level of language competency. Furthermore, without knowing the vocabulary, communicating in the second language becomes more difficult. As a result, learners with little vocabulary knowledge have significant challenges in learning English. Furthermore, the vocabulary used or acquired by humans determines their language. Thus, without vocabulary, students will be demotivated to utilize the language.

Vocabulary Form. The vocabulary form indicator's according to the results of this study. This result is indicative that the respondents' vocabulary knowledge in terms of form is rated as low. The students shared their perceptions of which they said that students struggle in word pronunciation, grammar rules, sentence structure and spelling. This is in congruence with the study of Afzal (2019), he investigated the difficulties faced by students in learning English vocabulary. He asserts the problems such as pronouncing and spelling words (written and spoken forms do not match most of the time), choosing appropriate meanings of words (complexity of vocabulary knowledge), inflections of word forms, (inadequate understanding of grammar), and an excessive number of words that students need to learn. It also reveals some important factors of difficulty in learning the vocabulary and attributes learning difficulties to various levels of language. To cite, these areas include learning the vocabulary meanings, pronunciation, spelling, using synonyms, and antonyms.

Furthermore, Lei and Reynolds (2022) supports the notion that students with insufficient vocabulary proficiency hinder their ability to accurately spell unfamiliar words, as they may not have encountered them frequently enough to internalize their spelling patterns. Similarly, without familiarity with a diverse vocabulary, students may struggle to pronounce words correctly, particularly if they have not heard them spoken aloud often. Understanding and applying grammatical rules can be challenging when students lack vocabulary knowledge, as many grammatical concepts rely on using specific words in appropriate contexts. This limitation extends to sentence

structure as well without a vast vocabulary, students may find it difficult to construct varied and grammatically correct sentences. In this sense, building vocabulary proficiency is foundational to mastering spelling, pronunciation, grammar, and sentence structure, all of which are integral components to support students in overcoming these difficulties and enhancing their building vocabulary proficiency is foundational to mastering spelling, pronunciation, grammar, and sentence structure, all of which are integral components to support students in overcoming these difficulties and enhancing their vocabulary formation skills.

Vocabulary Meaning. The respondents' vocabulary knowledge level in terms of meaning is low. This result is related to their abilities to comprehend a word. This connotes that the respondents find the vocabulary meaning as one of the challenges they faced towards vocabulary learning. In agreement with the study conducted by Susanto and Suhardianto (2018), they asserted that in language learning, vocabulary knowledge is considered as a dominant factor, either as a second or a foreign language. Vocabulary knowledge is justified as a crucial site to overall language acquisition process. There are a lot of unknown words that language learners encounter while they are reading. In this notion, the learner may have difficulties in comprehending the text they are reading.

In agreement with the study conducted by Khasawneh (2019), it is evident that vocabulary encompasses a vast array of words, including those with multiple meanings, abstract concepts, and specialized terminology. Students may struggle to grasp the intricacies of these words, especially if they lack prior knowledge of the word. They also claimed that having insufficient vocabulary knowledge was the main obstacle students faced as they tend to struggle in understanding the word. These findings support the notion that children with poorly-meaning words are very close to failing to understand the text because of the lack of decoding skills.

Vocabulary Use. The students' vocabulary knowledge level in terms of use is low. This signifies poor vocabulary can hinder comprehension, making it harder for students to understand new words and incorporate them into their own speech and writing. These students shared their perceptions that without an extensive vocabulary, they will be unable to use the words they have learned for comprehensible communication. Alqhani (2018) agree to this notion, he asserted that vocabulary knowledge is often viewed as a critical tool for second language learners because a limited vocabulary often impedes successful communication. In classroom, the achieving students possess the most sufficient vocabulary. By acknowledging the importance of vocabulary learning, he highlighted that learning vocabulary is essential for successful language use and plays an important role in the formation of complete spoken and written texts because without an extensive vocabulary, students were unable to use the structures and functions of words they have learned for comprehensible communication.

Aligned with the findings presented by Viera (2018), vocabulary knowledge is viewed as an essential tool for mastering any language skills; it also contributes to the understanding of written and spoken texts. While more frequent the exposure to vocabulary is, learners are more confident to understand and interpret the meaning of some unknown words from context. Therefore, learning vocabulary does not only mean the learning of new words but also to know their functions and applicability to different contexts and situations. Also, being aware of when it's appropriate to use certain words or expressions in different situations. In other words, it's not just about knowing the language, but also knowing how to use it effectively in real-life situations. This finding implied that building vocabulary skills is crucial for improving vocabulary production and overall language proficiency.

The Perception of Secondary Students with Regards to Their Vocabulary Knowledge

The perception of secondary students with regards to their vocabulary knowledge was shown in the previous chapter. Notably, different issues were probed which provoked various core ideas which were grouped into categories. This aimed to have a better understanding on the perceptions of the secondary students towards their vocabulary knowledge. With this, different propositions from the different authors and theorists were presented relative to their perceptions.

Psychological Factors. The secondary students shared their perceptions on how the psychological factors such as their motivations, interests, and behaviors influence their will to learn vocabulary. According to students motivated learners are more likely learn new words than those unmotivated learners. This result finds support in the Self-Determination Theory (STD), proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985). According to the Self-Determination Theory, this theory influences how motivated students are to learn vocabulary. When students feel they have choices in their learning, like choosing learning materials or methods, they feel more engaged and motivated. Also, when they perceive themselves as competent in learning vocabulary, they feel more motivated towards vocabulary learning. Moreover, when students feel connected and respected in their learning environment, they are more likely to be motivated to participate to learn new words without having fear of committing mistakes. Overall, by considering students' need for choice, competence, and connection, educators can boost their motivation for vocabulary learning, leading to proficient and confidence in language skills.

Moreover, the present finding further supports the notions put forth by Joung et al. (2022) which states that when students experience emotional satisfaction from learning new words, they are more likely to feel a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment, which in turn enhances their motivation to continue learning. Motivation is also a key factor that influences vocabulary learning. When students are motivated to learn new words they are more likely to invest time and effort to seek out opportunities to expand their vocabulary and are more receptive to various vocabulary learning strategies. Conversely, if students are not motivated to learn vocabulary in reading and listening in classroom and especially in incidental learning, the gap in vocabulary knowledge will be larger and subsequently is likely to hinder academic achievement for years to come.

Challenges towards Vocabulary Learning. It was revealed in the study that the students faced challenges with regards to vocabulary

learning such as difficulties in vocabulary comprehension and vocabulary formation. This finding aligns with the Word Recognition Theory, proposed by Rumelhart and McClelland (1986). The Word Recognition Theory suggests that when individuals encounter new words, their brains rapidly process various features of the word simultaneously, such as its spelling, pronunciation, and meaning. However, if students lack vocabulary knowledge, their ability to efficiently recognize and comprehend words may be hindered. This can lead to difficulties in reading comprehension, as well as slower and less accurate word recognition. Therefore, building vocabulary knowledge is crucial for enhancing word recognition skills and overall reading proficiency.

Consequently, the present finding further strengthens the argument made by Elttayef & Hussein (2018) which revealed that there are challenges faced by Arab language educators when teaching the universal language. One issue that educators faced is that students have difficulty understanding simple information regardless of whether English is taught in schools. Second, it demonstrates the teachers' disinterest in stressing the significance of the English language or the use of vocabulary words in the four corners of a classroom. This findings, shows that many students experience trouble working out vocabulary skills, most likely speaking and listening skills, and also points to teacher and curriculum concerns.

Vocabulary Proficiency Level. The findings revealed that some students recognized the extent of their vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary proficiency, from being high, neutral, or low. This observation is in line with the Vocabulary Breadth Theory of Michael Graves (1986), suggests that individuals with a wider range of vocabulary, encompassing a large number of words across different domains and topics, tend to exhibit higher levels of vocabulary proficiency. This theory emphasizes the significance of quantity when it comes to vocabulary knowledge. According to this perspective, having access to a diverse array of words enables individuals to better understand and express themselves in various contexts, leading to enhanced language comprehension, communication skills, and overall literacy proficiency compared to those individuals who possess shallower vocabulary.

Furthermore, this aligns with the findings of Shahid et al. (2023). The study revealed that students with high or adequate vocabulary knowledge levels typically possess a broader range of words and are more adept at understanding and using language in various contexts. They can comprehend complex texts, express themselves effectively, and engage in sophisticated discussions. While students with low vocabulary knowledge levels may struggle with understanding and expressing themselves, particularly when encountering unfamiliar words or complex texts. They may have difficulty comprehending reading materials, expressing their thoughts clearly, and participating actively in discussions.

The Insights of Secondary Students with Regards to Their Vocabulary Knowledge Dynamic Language Enrichment. The secondary students emphasize the importance of ongoing language exposure, meaningful interactions with texts, discussions, and experiences that foster vocabulary growth over time. This approach involves not only learning new words but also understanding their meanings, exploring their usage in different contexts, and making connections between words and concepts. The findings demonstrated that students recognize that vocabulary development is a dynamic and lifelong process that evolves through continuous learning and engagement with language. This finding aligns with the Vocabulary Exposure Theory, proposed by Davis (1989). The theory asserted that individuals acquire vocabulary knowledge primarily through repeated exposure to words in meaningful contexts. The more frequently individuals encounter words in reading, listening, speaking, and writing activities, the more likely they are to learn and retain those words. Moreover, vocabulary exposure theory emphasizes the importance of immersive language experiences, such as reading widely across different genres, engaging in conversations, and participating in activities that require the use of language. By exposing oneself to a rich variety of words in diverse contexts, individuals can expand their vocabulary repertoire and enhance their language proficiency over time.

Moreover, the present finding further strengthens the argument made by Aggazi (2022) by highlighting that learning a vocabulary is a component within the language domain that holds significant for student's engagement in language acquisition and those endeavoring to gain proficiency in a new language. Therefore, the study outlines the significant data on the effectiveness of vocabulary while also discussing various interesting approaches employed by English teachers when teaching English to young learners. The results showed that, learners learn a new word by listening to people say and trying to practice it and they found that the use of games will assist young learners in absorbing the lesson while having fun, allowing them to quickly recall all of the languages. Despite the fact that games are quite popular among young students, they should not be utilized unnecessarily. They should be selected based on the level, interest, and context of the learners. It must also be concerned with the topic and vocabulary offered. Any game can be useful if it is suited to the topic and overseen by a knowledgeable and professional teacher.

Achieved Academic Excellence. The students have shown favorable views on the importance of vocabulary knowledge to achieving academic excellence. Students emphasize that having sufficient vocabulary enhances their classroom participation and help them for academic endeavors. This observation finds support in Strategic Investment Theory of Nation (1990) which suggests that that learners should prioritize the acquisition of high-frequency vocabulary items, which are commonly used in academic texts and discussions. By strategically investing their time and effort in mastering these key words, students can enhance their ability to comprehend academic materials, participate in classroom discussions, and express themselves effectively in all forms of communication. Since academic success often hinges on a strong command of language, focusing on high-frequency vocabulary can be particularly beneficial for students striving to excel academically. By mastering the vocabulary that is most commonly encountered in academic contexts, students can build a solid foundation for success across various subjects and academic tasks.

This finding is in line with the research conducted by McLeod et al. (2019), which highlights the vocabulary use as the deliberation of an effective application of words within written or spoken communication. Hence, students can exercise conveying their ideas, thoughts, and emotions with precision and clarity. Additionally, students are required for an extent exposure with various materials that has in relation with immersing oneself to the language in expanding their linguistic repertoire. Therefore, it suggests that teachers must have strategies align with the utilization of vocabulary during class sessions for the students contributing a great impact supporting the student's development for vocabulary and outcomes

Vocabulary Knowledge Advancement. The secondary students recognized the importance of enhancing their vocabulary knowledge by learning new words and understanding their meanings and usage contexts to achieve success in communication and academic endeavors. The findings aligned with the Usage-Based Theory of Tomasello (2003), offers valuable insights into how learners acquire and expand their lexical repertoire. This theory suggests that as learners engage with words in diverse contexts and situations, they develop a multifaceted understanding of vocabulary usage. By actively encountering new words in authentic contexts, such as through reading, listening, speaking, and writing, learners internalize the meanings and usage patterns of words. Through repeated exposure, active engagement, and meaningful language use, learners advance their vocabulary knowledge, drawing on the principles of the Usage-Based Theory to inform their language learning journey.

Consequently, the present finding further supports the notions put forth by Rashid et al. (2022) that students could not comprehend other's ideas or communicate their own if they did not have a broad vocabulary. Hence, the study highlighted the significance of learning vocabulary meaning to the extent of students, in such it increases their word awareness and fluency of the certain language. Further, knowledge of vocabulary meaning is among the most critical language learning skills as its firms to stand as the foundational strength of communication. Therefore, it is fundamental for students to have knowledge of the exact vocabulary meaning since, it serves as factor in using the certain language efficiently.

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The results of the quantitative and qualitative study were connected in each focal point, as revealed the findings of both phases of the study. With this, axiological implications were developed specifically on assessing secondary students' vocabulary knowledge.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. Students assessed the level of their vocabulary knowledge as low in terms of vocabulary proficiency. This result is indicative that the vocabulary knowledge level of secondary students is low. This is in congruence with the study of Afzal (2019), in which he highlights that without much knowledge of vocabulary, it is difficult to attain any language proficiency. Furthermore, without learning the vocabulary, communication in the second language becomes harder. As such, low vocabulary knowledge poses severe problems to its learners, which consequently impedes the learning of the English language.

Moreover, the findings agree with the study conducted by Aggazi (2022) that in an academic context, students with limited vocabulary may struggle to understand the meaning of texts, leading to difficulties in comprehending assignments, answering questions, and analyzing content. This can impede their ability to grasp key concepts and engage critically with course material. Similarly, in subjects like science, social studies, and mathematics, academic success often hinges on understanding specialized terminology and complex instructions, which can pose challenges for students with restricted vocabulary. Additionally, low vocabulary levels can hinder effective communication in both spoken and written forms, affecting participation in class discussions, presentations, and essay writing. As a result, students may experience lower grades, reduced confidence, and a sense of academic frustration.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. The findings asserted that students' vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary form is rated as low. This highlights that difficulties in vocabulary formation were considered one of the challenges faced by the secondary students towards vocabulary learning. This result was supported by the study conducted by Afzal (2019). He asserts that there are problems such as pronouncing and spelling words (written and spoken forms do not match most of the time), choosing appropriate meanings of words (complexity of vocabulary knowledge), inflections of word forms (inadequate understanding of grammar), and an excessive number of words that students need to learn. It also reveals some important factors of difficulty in learning vocabulary and attributes learning difficulties to various levels of language. To cite, these areas include learning vocabulary meanings, pronunciation, spelling, using synonyms, and antonyms.

Furthermore, Lei and Reynolds (2022) support the notion that students with insufficient vocabulary proficiency hinder their ability to accurately spell unfamiliar words, as they may not have encountered them frequently enough to internalize their spelling patterns. Similarly, without familiarity with a diverse vocabulary, students may struggle to pronounce words correctly, particularly if they have not heard them spoken aloud often.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. The result of the study revealed that students' vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary meaning is considered low. These findings showed that vocabulary comprehension was also one of the challenges faced by secondary students towards vocabulary learning. This connotes that the respondents find vocabulary meaning to be one of the challenges they faced in learning vocabulary. In relation to the study conducted by Susanto and Suhardianto (2018), they asserted that in language learning, there are a lot of unknown words that language learners encounter while they are reading. In this sense, the learner may have difficulties comprehending the text they are reading.

Moreover, in agreement with the study conducted by Khasawneh (2019), it is evident that vocabulary encompasses a vast array of words, including those with multiple meanings, abstract concepts, and specialized terminology. Students may struggle to grasp the intricacies of these words, especially if they lack prior knowledge of the word. They also claimed that having insufficient vocabulary knowledge was the main obstacle students faced, as they tend to struggle with understanding words. These findings support the notion that children with poorly-meaning words are very close to failing to understand the text because of a lack of decoding skills.

Students' Vocabulary Knowledge. The findings revealed that students' vocabulary meaning is rated as low. Hence, poor vocabulary can hinder vocabulary comprehension, making it harder for students to understand new words and incorporate them into their own speech and writing. Alqhani (2018) agrees with this notion, in which he emphasizes that vocabulary knowledge is often viewed as a critical tool for second language learners because a limited vocabulary often impedes successful communication. In the classroom, the achieving students possess the most sufficient vocabulary. By acknowledging the importance of vocabulary learning, he highlighted that learning vocabulary is essential for successful language use and plays an important role in the formation of complete spoken and written texts because, without an extensive vocabulary, students are unable to use the structures and functions of words they have learned for comprehensible communication.

Aligned with the findings presented by Viera (2018), which highlighted that learning vocabulary does not only mean the learning of new words but also knowing their functions and applicability to different contexts and situations. Also, be aware of when it's appropriate to use certain words or expressions in different situations. In other words, it's not just about knowing the language but also knowing how to use it effectively in real-life situations. This finding implies that building vocabulary skills is crucial for improving vocabulary production and overall language proficiency.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. First, the status of students' vocabulary knowledge is low in terms of vocabulary form, vocabulary meaning, and vocabulary use. Hence, this indicates that the indicators of vocabulary knowledge is considered low.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based on the responses gained through the conduct of an in-depth interview (IDI) and a focus group discussion (FGD). The results gave more information about the students' perceptions with regards to their vocabulary knowledge. Qualitatively, secondary students have shared their perceptions of the importance of vocabulary knowledge and its impact on their academic performance. The following themes were emerged: Psychological Factors, Challenges Towards Vocabulary Learning, and Vocabulary Proficiency Level.

Third, from the participants responses, other themes are identified, which show the insights shared by secondary students with regards to how they can enhance their vocabulary knowledge and how teachers' strategies can help them with vocabulary learning. The following are the themes: Dynamic Language Enrichment, Achieved Academic Excellence, and Vocabulary Knowledge Advancement.

Lastly, to better understand the students' perceptions towards vocabulary knowledge, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The status of Vocabulary Knowledge based on the quantitative results shows that it converged with the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both of the quantitative and qualitative results confirm that the vocabulary knowledge of secondary students is low. Hence, they faced challenges in terms of vocabulary formation, understanding the meaning of words, and appropriate use of words in context.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the status of vocabulary knowledge reveals that among the three indicators of vocabulary knowledge, vocabulary use has the lowest mean, which affects students' ability to use the words appropriately, it is recommended that students develop their reading habits, such as in books and dictionaries, as it exposes students to new words and help them understand how these words are used in sentences and paragraphs. They may also actively engage in conversations and discussions with their peers or teachers in English, as it would provide them with practical opportunities to apply their newly learned words effectively. Furthermore, teachers should foster a dynamic and supportive learning environment by integrating interactive learning to facilitate students, such as games, discussions, and group tasks, as these allow students to actively participate in using new words in context, making the learning process more enjoyable and effective. These activities also encourage collaboration and communication among students, providing opportunities for peer interaction and shared learning experiences that can boost their confidence in using the words in context.

Moreover, based on the results of the qualitative phase on the perceptions of secondary students with regards to their vocabulary knowledge, students should motivate themselves to learn new words through constant reading of books and dictionaries, as this gives them the opportunity to encounter a vast range of words that help them understand their meaning and their use. They can also watch videos from online platforms relative to vocabulary learning and search on Google for a wider and deeper understanding of unfamiliar words. Moreover, it is also beneficial for students to play games that can enrich their vocabulary knowledge, like playing word escapes, as this helps them expand their vocabulary and understand how to associate words in a specific context. Additionally, students must practice applying learned words in a conversation or in a discussion, as this allows them to develop their language skills and vocabulary proficiency.

Furthermore, various insights shared by secondary students with regards to vocabulary knowledge may be helpful to their academic progress. Students have to motivate themselves to continue learning new words to expand their vocabulary knowledge, which prepares them for future academic endeavors. Through this, students become more confident in participating in classroom engagement and excel academically.

In addition, the researcher recommends that students implement several strategies to effectively enhance their vocabulary knowledge. First, students should read constantly, as this exposes students to diverse vocabulary in different contexts, helping them understand word usage and meanings effectively. Additionally, students should learn how to use context clues to infer the meaning of unfamiliar words while reading, fostering independent vocabulary growth. Incorporating interactive vocabulary apps and games can make learning engaging and enjoyable, motivating students to actively participate in their learning process. Moreover, it is beneficial for students to create personalized vocabulary lists, record new words with definitions and example sentences, and regularly review them to retain the words easily.

Lastly, teachers are important for students' vocabulary development. Hence, it is recommended that teachers provide constructive feedback by providing students with specific guidance and support to improve their language skills. Also, engage students in reading and writing activities such as reading books and writing essays to develop vocabulary proficiency. Furthermore, teachers must encourage students to utilize English as a medium of communication in classroom interaction for them to develop their ability to use their learned words appropriately. By employing these strategies collectively, students can develop a robust vocabulary repertoire essential for academic success and effective communication.

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